

Study on Opinion of Trainee Teachers Towards the Provision of NEP-2020 with Reference to Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities in Higher Education

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

There are so many Acts and policies passed by the Govt. of India and are being executed on grass root level for qualitative change in education and rehabilitation of persons with and without disabilities. This study focuses on one objective and two hypotheses. The selected objective is to examine trainee teacher's opinions on the provisions outlined in the National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education. The two hypotheses are: (1) There will be no significant differences in trainee teachers' opinions regarding the provisions in NEP 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education. (2) There will be no significant differences in opinions toward NEP 2020 based on trainee teacher's age. The study is based on 40 trainee teachers from different Universities of Uttar Pradesh who were enrolled in

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M.Ed. Special Education. A descriptive survey method was employed, and data analysis was conducted using the chi-square test. The results indicate that both hypotheses were rejected, meaning there are no significant differences in opinions. This paper highlights the role of teachers in the implementation of education policy.

Keywords: NEP 2020; inclusion; higher education; trainee teachers; opinion study.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education forms the cornerstone of human life. It not only ensures individual development but also plays a key role in the overall advancement of society. Since the ancient times, education has been regarded as a lifelong process that shapes an individual's personality, character, and habits. Aristotle described education as "the creation of a sound mind in a sound body," while Swami Vivekananda viewed it as "the manifestation of perfection already inherent in man." India's educational history is ancient, with systems of higher education dating back to 1000 BCE. In the modern era, British colonialism shaped the education system, but post-independence, India developed its own policies. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) replaces the 34-year-old policy and emphasizes inclusive education specifically for persons with disabilities; the policy promotes their inclusion in higher education through provisions such as specialized resources, training, and reservations.

1.1 Concept and Importance of Education

Education has been defined variously by philosophers. Rousseau saw it as the expression of an individual's inner powers. John Dewey described it as a means to control the environment and fulfill possibilities. In India, education is divided into primary, secondary, and higher levels. Primary education provides foundational skills like reading, writing and calculation. Secondary education bridges primary and higher levels, while higher education focuses on specialized subjects, such as undergraduate and postgraduate studies. The history of higher education is influenced by Europe, where systems in France and Germany are state-controlled. In India, higher education began with the first universities were established in 1857. NEP 2020 aims to increase the gross enrollment ratio in higher education up to 50%.

1.2 Concept of Inclusion and Disability

Inclusion in education involves integrating all students without discrimination. It values diversity and provides equal opportunities. Principles of inclusion encompass equality and acceptance of individual differences. According to Tuli (2013),

inclusion is the process of addressing children's needs within schools. Disability, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), arises from impairment, disability, and handicap. Impairment refers to physical or mental loss, disability to inability to perform tasks, and handicap to social barriers. In India, the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016 includes 21 categories of disabilities, offering benefits to individuals with 40% or more disability.

1.3 Provisions in the NEP 2020

NEP 2020 was prepared by the K. Kasturirangan Committee. As the first policy of the 21st century, it targets 6% of GDP allocation for education. Provisions for persons with disabilities include specialized training, infrastructure (e.g., ramps, Braille), free education (ages 6-18), and inclusive curricula. Under the provision of Rashtriya Uchchatar Shiksha Abhiyan (RUSA) persons with disabilities are being included in higher education system but through this policy rehabilitation and social inclusion for students with disabilities need to be increased.

1.4 Rationale of the Study

According to Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016, 21 categories of disabilities replaces the Persons with Disabilities Act 1995. The numbers of persons with disabilities have been increased but it has also noticed that all the provisions and policies are failed to meet out their targeted goals especially with reference to children with marginalized section due to lack of knowledge of individuals and ignorance of the executing authorities. There are also lots of barriers for the children with disabilities which highly affect their education right from primary to higher education level. The present study highlights the dire need of persons with disabilities in higher education system.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rakshit and Yadav (2025) investigate inclusive education practices aligned with NEP 2020. The study outlines key principles like equity, UDL, teacher training, and community engagement to foster inclusive environments. Overall, it offers a valuable framework for implementation of NEP

2020 in inclusive mandates, promoting equity and empowerment in education. Shravan (2025) studied on NEP-2020's provisions with reference to inclusive education at higher level in India. The result indicates that NEP-2020 promotes to access, scholarships and technological integration and also persistent challenges in low enrollment. The study also recommends about the financial aid expansion and diversify curriculum. Aneraye et al. (2024) examine the impact of NEP 2020 on inclusive education for individuals with disabilities. This study highlights key provisions like flexible curricula, teacher training, assistive technologies, and community engagement to foster equitable learning environments. Singh and Jaiswal (2024) provide a comprehensive analysis of challenges and opportunities for Implementing NEP 2020 in the higher education sector. It highlights benefits like multidisciplinary curricula, technology integration, teacher training, and community engagement to promote equity, innovation, and global competitiveness. It addresses obstacles such as infrastructure gaps, funding shortages, resistance to change, and skills. Sharma and Joshi (2024) had studied on NEP-2020's key provisions and implications for learners with disabilities. In this study it was found that the policy focuses inclusive classroom, early intervention, special education, assistive technologies, vocational training, and teacher orientation programme. Sharma and Bala (2022) investigate awareness of NEP 2020 among secondary school teachers in Kangra district through a survey. Findings indicate average awareness levels, with no significant differences across government/private schools, gender, teaching experience, or arts/science streams, based on t-tests. The study have done by Varshney and Ahlawat (2022) on the vision of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 for inclusive education in India, with a particular focus on socio-economically disadvantaged groups. The study found that the dropout rate of learner has declined due to positive actions. The NEP-2020 has also reinforces equity through targeted groups. A study have done by the Sharma et al. (2022) on the topic of explored university teachers' perceptions of inclusive education in Pune, India. In this study the researches have collected 309 faculty members as sample of various universities through online questionnaire. The study found no significant differences among the institution types. While the other hand the frequent interactions with persons with disabilities found significant positive impact

on teacher's attitude towards inclusion. Kalyani (2020) examine the NEP-2020, comparing it with previous education policies to assess its impact on nation-building, growth, development, and independence. Using a questionnaire with 30 questions based on a 5-point rating scale, the study analyzes responses to assess the policy's impact. The findings indicate a need for significant reform after 34 years, highlighting visible changes in the education system.

2.1 Objective

To study the trainee teachers opinion towards the provisions of NEP 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education.

2.2 Hypotheses

- 1 There will be no significant differences in trainee teachers opinion regarding the provisions in NEP 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education.
- 2 There will be no significant differences in opinions toward NEP 2020 based on trainee teachers gender

3. METHODOLOGY

The study is non- experimental under survey method was used. The sample was heterogeneous and the purposive sampling method was used for the study. The total 40 trainees (20 males, 20 females) were selected for the present study. Self made and validated by the subject expert Likert 5 point scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree) opinionnaire with 30 items were used with targeting NEP 2020 provisions in inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education. The samples were collected from different Universities of Uttar Pradesh who were enrolled in M.Ed. Special Education. The data was collected after the proper approval of concerned authorities. The data was analyzed by using the mean, SD, SEM and 't' test under the non- parametric statistical test.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis-1- There will be no significant differences in trainee teacher's opinion regarding the provisions in NEP 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education.

Table 1. One-sample t-test

Test	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t-score
One-sample t-test	40	110.73 (90 neutral)	16.02	2.534	8.18

Table 1. Details of the mean and SD of the obtained data from samples regarding the opinion of trainee teachers towards the National Education Policy 2020.

From the above Table-1, the data shows that the mean of the total samples based on the data obtained from the opinion of trainee teachers towards the provisions described in the National Education Policy 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education is 110.73 (SD=16.02). Since $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference, with trainee teachers expressing positive opinions (above neutral) toward NEP 2020 provisions. The rejection of Hypothesis-1 ($p < 0.001$) indicates that trainee teachers hold significantly positive opinions on NEP 2020 provisions for PwD inclusion in higher education. This suggests normal approval of policies, though the score is not exceptionally high, possibly reflecting practical implementation on the grass root level.

Hypothesis-2-There will be no significant differences in opinions toward NEP 2020 based on trainee teacher's gender.

Table- 2: Details of the mean and SD of the obtained data from samples regarding the opinion of trainee teachers towards the National Education Policy 2020 gender wise

Table2. Compare group mean

Group	N	Mean	SD	SEM	t
Male	20	108.15	17.09	3.82	
Female	20	113.30	15.39	3.44	-1.54

From the observation of the Table-2, it is clear that the mean of the group based on the data obtained from the opinion of trainee teachers towards the provisions described in the National Education Policy 2020 for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education is 108.15 (SD=17.09) for male and 113.30(SD=15.39) for female. Since $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference, with trainee teachers expressing positive opinions toward NEP 2020 provisions. The rejection of Hypothesis-1 ($p < 0.001$) indicates that trainee teachers hold significantly positive

opinions on NEP 2020 provisions for PwD inclusion. The result also suggests that the NEP 2020 provisions are helpful in inclusion of persons with disabilities in higher education. Hypothesis-2, the non-significant result shows that gender does not influence opinions, despite females having a slightly higher mean. This uniformity indicates that the shared training experiences of both male and female teacher education programs emphasize on inclusive education principles equally on the basis of gender.

Interpreting results and comparing them with existing data is a crucial part of this study, as it not only validates the findings but also offers directions for future research and policy-making. In this section the results for Objective and Hypothesis-1 (no significant differences in provisions) and Hypothesis-2 (no significant differences in opinions based on gender). From the null Hypothesis-1, the overall mean opinion score was 110.73 (SD=16.02), indicate a positive response with relation to the maximum score of 150. This suggests that trainee teacher's opinion towards NEP 2020 provisions as suitable for including persons with disabilities in higher education. The One-sample t test for Hypothesis-1 accepts the null hypothesis, meaning no significant differences in opinions on provisions. This implies uniform support among trainee teachers, strengthening the policy's acceptance. In the context of Hypothesis-2, mean of male and female was found 108.15 and 113.30 respectively. The calculated 't' value was 1.54 indicating rejection of the null hypothesis. This result reveals that female trainee teachers are more positive towards the NEP-2020 in inclusion of higher education than male trainee teachers.

5. CONCLUSION

Finally it is clear from the study that the trainee teachers shows mixed type of opinion towards the implementation of NEP 2020 provisions for the inclusion PwD in higher education. No significant difference was noticed on the basis of gender. On the principles of something is better than nothing these findings suggest broad support for the policy within the samples through the professional training. To strengthen implementation, teacher education programs

should address potential concerns through practical training. Further studies are recommended to assess opinions across diverse regions and include qualitative insights for a deeper understanding about the attitudinal, infrastructural and social barriers.

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Authors hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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